

IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF EXPERIMENTAL EXERCISES RECOMMENDED TO INCREASE THE LEG STRENGTH OF BREASTSTROKERS

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Abstract. In this article, the methodology for the development of strength readiness among young men specializing in swimming training has been improved and introduced.

Key words: Control tests, way breaststroke, experimental group, control group, pedagogical observation.

Importance. In recent years, in order to popularize physical education and sports, to promote a healthy lifestyle among the population, to create the necessary conditions for the physical rehabilitation of people with limited opportunities, and to ensure the country's proper participation in international sports arenas consistent measures have been taken in the republic.

At the same time, the implementation of exact programs that mainly serve to strengthen the overall health rate of the population in the field of physical education and sports, the wide involvement of young people in sports and the selection of talented athletes from among them, the formation of national teams with skilled athletes who provide high results in sports, and an additional condition for trainers can be said as an urgent issue today without doubt.

One of the main factors of young swimmers in swimming is strength training. Manifestation of power potential in swimming is often determined by the mechanism of generation of propulsive force. Various training tools aimed at special strength training significantly affect the movement system of the main skill. The manifestation of strength is necessarily related to physiological and biochemical processes. That is, together with the efferent nervous system, it is manifested under the influence of other physiological and biochemical processes. If we look at the context of the interaction of these two components, then the superiority of the first component (explosion) over the second (power) is noticeable. Because the manifestation of power is the mechanism of its activation. At the same time, the strength of the swimmer can be increased by increasing the absolute strength of the muscle. Slow muscle activity is not only harmful to health, but also delays the development of the body. One of the important factors in the growth of sports achievements is the improvement of leg strength of breaststroke swimmers. However, it is not an exaggeration to say that breaststroke is one of the most difficult strokes for many swimmers, because breaststroke requires strong legs and coordinated and symmetrical movements. Therefore, the search for new ways to improve strength in breaststroke swimming is one of the most urgent issues. It can be seen from all the above that the scientific-methodical approach to solving this problem is not enough at the moment. Therefore, the development of a set of exercises aimed at improving the strength training of breaststrokers in swimming circles is considered a rather urgent problem.

Purpose of work. Determining the effectiveness of measuring leg strength of brass swimmers through special exercises.

Research tasks:

During the research, the following tasks were defined in order to achieve the goal set before us:

1. Selection of control tests to determine leg strength indicators of swimmers in the brass method;
2. Determination of leg strength of swimmers on the basis of selected test controls;
3. Justification of the effectiveness of the set of exercises aimed at increasing the leg strength of swimmers.

Research object. Swimmers of the 2nd Children's and Adolescent Sports School in Yashnabad District, Tashkent.

Research methods. In order to solve the goals and tasks set for our research, the following methods were used:

- Comparative analysis and generalization of scientific methodical literature and regulatory documents related to the topic.
- Organization of pedagogical observations and current researches;
- Conducting pedagogical control tests;
- Using methods of mathematical statistics.

Organization of the study: The study was conducted from September 2021 to December 2022 in the 1st Children's and Adolescent Sports School, Bektemir district, Tashkent city. The study was conducted during annual sports training. At the beginning of the experiment, the control and experimental groups were selected athletes with the same training. 20 swimmers of sports class II and III aged 12-13 took part in the experiments. Two groups were formed - control and experimental groups, each consisting of 10 people. The control group practiced swimming according to the standard program, the experimental group used a special set of exercises developed by us.

The following tests were selected to monitor the strength training of swimmers and were used in the experimental and control groups.

1. Standing long jump (cm).
2. Measurement of the force of gravity in the water (only in the movement of the legs) (kg).
3. Measurement of gravity in water (in full coordination) (kg).
4. 25 m swimming in breaststroke (legs only) (seconds).
5. 25 m breaststroke (in full coordination) (seconds).
6. 50 m breaststroke (in full coordination) (seconds).

Testing of such strength qualities is an important organizational and guiding factor in the process of physical training of breaststroke swimmers and serves to control the development of physical qualities. One of the indicators representing the development of physical qualities is defined as the satisfactory passing of tests by athletes.

Strength training in swimming sports is based on general theoretical views of sports training. Therefore, strength training methods should match those used in both water and land training. A rubber shock absorber that stretches in water is widely used as a means of strength training for swimmers in water.

Summary. The following conclusions can be made based on the results of the research.

Summarizing the above points, researching the characteristics of the methodological foundations of the formation of the strength movement ability of swimmers in quick-power sports is a certain skill in solving important life issues in sports.

As the leg muscles develop in breaststroke swimming, their swimming speed improves. In the brass method, if the brass elements are regularly performed in the rubber, the correct and strong execution of the technique will play an important role in achieving high results in the future.

At the initial stage of training, they should take a responsible approach to learning different options for developing leg strength in breaststroke swimming.

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